

Gastronomic tourism: a comparative analysis of the literature

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to investigate how gastronomic tourism has been approached in academic productions both nationally and internationally. The research used a qualitative methodology, with emphasis on bibliographic research, carried out on the journal portal of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES). The search was directed to the period from 1990 to 2022, in order to gather the theoretical support necessary to deepen the understanding of the theme. 25 articles that were most aligned with the object of study were selected. The results indicate that scientific research on gastronomic tourism is recent, covering a period of about three decades, with different approaches and perspectives. The presence of convergent and divergent points was found between the articles, addressing aspects such as cultural identity, symbolic values and socioeconomic development. However, the main focus of the research was the analysis of the materials and methods used in the selected academic productions, which allow us to understand the most recurrent methodological approaches in the investigation of gastronomic tourism.

Key words: Gastronomic tourism, gastronomic experiences, methodology, comparative analysis.

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Introduction

Gastronomic tourism has been consolidated as an important aspect within the field of tourism, reflecting not only the search for sensory experiences, but also the desire to understand and experience cultural traditions, regional identities and social practices through food. In recent years, the growing appreciation of local gastronomy as a tourist attraction has driven the development of new academic approaches and professional practices that seek to understand this phenomenon in a multidisciplinary way.

The literature on gastronomic tourism, although still expanding, already presents a significant volume of studies that analyze the relationship between tourism and cuisine. These studies explore different dimensions, such as the socioeconomic impact of gastronomic tourism in the regions

visited, the preservation and promotion of cultural identities, and the dynamics of consumption and behavior of tourists. However, the theoretical and methodological approaches adopted vary considerably, reflecting the diversity of cultural and socioeconomic contexts around the world.

In this article, we propose a comparative analysis of the literature on gastronomic tourism, with the aim of identifying the main trends and gaps in academic productions both nationally and internationally. The research seeks to map the predominant approaches in the literature, examine the methodologies used and discuss the results and implications of existing studies. Understanding these aspects is essential for advancing knowledge about gastronomic tourism and for the formulation of policies and practices that integrate gastronomy with the tourism sector in a sustainable and innovative way.

This comparative analysis is expected to contribute to the development of a more consolidated field of study, which enables new approaches and solutions to the challenges faced by tourist destinations that seek to incorporate gastronomy as a central attraction, while preserving their cultural identities and promoting local socioeconomic development.

Methodology

The present work was developed from a bibliographic research carried out on the journal portal of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), with access authorized by the Federated Academic Community (CAFE), as it is a database that has a collection of national and international academic productions. The research was guided by the keyword “gastronomic tourism”, which directed the focus of the study.

The research is characterized as bibliographic, as defined by several authors, such as Gil (2002) and Marconi and Lakatos (2003), who understand it as an opportunity to improve knowledge based on already published works. In this context, the bibliographic research was used to gather information and data that would contribute to the theoretical contribution necessary to answer the central question: what does the scientific literature say about gastronomic tourism and in what way?

Articles in English, Spanish, and Portuguese, published in peer-reviewed journals, from 1990 to 2022, were analyzed. The time frame began in 1990, the year in which, according to Long (2018), tourism began to recognize gastronomy as one of the main tourist attractions and motivations.

The initial research was based on consulting the CAPES platform, in which 682 potentially relevant articles were identified. To ensure adherence to the theme, inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied. First, we analyzed the titles, abstracts and keywords to verify whether the studies specifically addressed gastronomic tourism. We then excluded articles that did not meet the research question, such as those that mentioned gastronomy tangentially or in contexts other than tourism. In addition, repeated studies and review articles without empirical depth were disregarded. After this refinement, 25 articles remained that were directly aligned with the proposed theme and were analyzed in depth.

These 25 selected articles were divided into research subareas, as described below:

- Gastronomic Route: 4 articles
- Dining Experience: 4 items
- Gastronomy and Tourism: 11 articles
- Gastronomic Destination: 6 items

These subareas are illustrated in Figure 1, which shows the distribution of the articles analyzed.

Figure 1. Sub-themes identified in the analyzed articles. Source: Prepared by the survey 2022.

The research in question has a qualitative nature, according to Fonseca (2002), who defines this method as one aimed at studying the specificities of a phenomenon, without the intention of establishing relationships between variables or formulating generalizations about the object of study. Thus, the focus of the research was directed to the understanding of particular aspects of the phenomenon, prioritizing the answer to the “how” instead of investigating the “why” of the occurrences.

The research field consisted of a set of 25 articles, 11 of which were written in Portuguese, 6 in English and 8 in Spanish, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that there was no selection of articles prior to 2012. Most publications occur in a recent period, specifically between 2017 and 2022, totaling 17 articles, with the following distribution: 2017 (1), 2018 (7), 2019 (1), 2020 (2), 2021 (2) and 2022 (4). Between 2012 and 2016, 8 articles were selected, distributed as follows: 2012 (2), 2013 (1), 2015 (2) and 2016 (3). No articles published in 2015 were selected, and 2018 saw the highest number of publications.

The journal *Rosa dos Ventos* stood out as the most prolific, with 3 articles published, followed by *Journal Tourism and Heritage Research*, with 2. The other journals presented only one article each. It should be noted that some articles were written in Spanish and published in journals that, although they publish mostly in English, accept contributions in Spanish.

Table 1. Articles that constituted the field of research.

AUTHOR	TITLE	MAGAZINE	YEAR
Uiara Martins; Ericka Amorim; Regina Schluter.	The promotion of Brazilian gastronomy in tourist brochures – an analysis of the case of the Lisbon tourism exchange (Btl 2012).	Compass Rose – RV.	2012
Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Emilio J. Morales-Fernández; Leonor María Pérez Naranjo.	Analysis of Gastronomic Tourism in the Province of Cordoba.	Tourism & Management Studies.	2012
Rosana Peccini	Gastronomy and tourism	Compass Rose – RV.	2013
Jaqueline Munchen; Roslaine Kovalczuk de Oliveira Garcia.	Travelers' interest in the gastronomic elements of tourism.	Online knowledge.	2015
Álvaro Augusto Bahls; Rodolfo Wendhausen Krause; Fernanda de Souza Farias.	Gastronomic Planning in Tourist Destinations: A Comparison between the National and Foreign Panorama.	Compass Rose – RV.	2015
Charlys Lima; Sueli Moreira; Alicia Cabral; Caroline Silva; Maria Luiza Mesquita.	Ginga with tapioca: gastronomy of the Redinha market as a tourist attraction.	Contemporary tourism – RTC.	2016
Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Ricardo Hernández Rojas; Virginia Navajas Romero.	The study of gastronomic tourism in Córdoba and the association of the Cuisine. An econometric analysis.	Tourism and Hospitality Management.	2016
Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Luis Amador; Juan Manuel Arjona Fuentes.	The protected designation of origin "Los Pedroches" as a gastronomic route of Iberian ham: analysis of the visitor profile and future evolution.	Cuadernos de desarrollo rural.	2016
Fabián Andrés Llano.	Gastronomy, tourism and territorial potentialities: the mining dish and salting, bases for food tourism in Nemocón.	Colombian Journal of Geography.	2017
Lucy m. Long.	Cultural policy in Gastronomic tourism with Ethnic foods.	Journal of business administration – PENSATAS.	2018
Mirna de Lima Medeiros; Júlio Araújo Carneiro da Cunha; João Luiz Passador.	Gastronomic tourism and regional development: a study based on the case of artisanal Minas cheese from Serro.	Virtual Tourism Dock – CVT.	2018
Sandra Cunha.	Gastronomic tourism, a differential factor.	Journal of Education. Technologies, and Health.	2018
Luz Mary Castellón Valdez; Joaquín Fontecha Fontecha.	Gastronomy: a source for the development of tourism and the strengthening of cultural identity in Santander.	Tourism and Society.	2018
María Teresa Kido Cruz; Isis Arlene Díaz Carrión; Antonio Kido Cruz.	Diner satisfaction as a key element of the gastronomy-tourism binômio in Tijuana.	Journal of Contemporary Food and Regional Development.	2018
Basilio Verduzco; Basilia Valenzuela.	Urban gastronomic-tourist districts, conflicts and problems of public management. Guadalajara, Mexico.	Regional Urban Studies – EURE.	2018
María del Carmen Navarrete Torres; Cecilia García Muñoz Aparicio.	Gastronomic tourism: flavour and tradition.	Journal of Tourism and Heritage Research.	2018
Chayenne Goes; Rúbia Gisele Tramontin Mascarenhas; Mirna de Lima Medeiros.	Flavors of Paraná: analysis of tourism promotion.	Revista Interprogramas de Pós-Graduação em Comunicação do Centro Oeste – ESFERAS.	2019
Maria Henriqueta Sperandio Garcia Gimenes Minasse.	Gastronomic Tourism as a research object: analysis of publications in Brazilian journals (2005-2017).	Brazilian Journal of Tourism Research – RBTUR.	2020

AUTHOR	TITLE	MAGAZINE	YEAR
Salvador Moral-Cuadra; Raquel Acero de la Cruz; Ramón Rueda López; Enrique Salinas Cuadrado.	Relationship between Consumer Motivation and the Gastronomic Experience of Olive Oil Tourism in Spain.	Sustainability.	2020
Anderson Sartori; Rosana Arruda Cruz; Luciano Tricarico.	Affective food memory: a concept for the development of experiences for gastronomic tourism.	Compass Rose – RV.	2021
Geneveva Dancausa Millán; Geneveva Milla'n Vázquez de la Torre; Ricardo Hernández Rojas.	Analysis of the demand for gastronomic tourism in Andalusia (Spain).	Plos One	2021
Janet Chang; Bendegul Okumus; Chih-Hung Wang; Chien-Yin Chiu.	Food tourism: cooking Holiday experiences in East Asia.	Tourism Review	2021
Daniel de Jesús Contreras; F. Xavier Medina.	Gastronomic tourism, typical agri-food products and designations of origin. Possibilities And Expectations Of Development In Mexico.	Journal of Tourism and Heritage Research.	2021
Elisangela de Farias; Adrielly Souza Silva; Marconi Freitas da Costa.	Factors that influence tourists to ecogastronomic destinations.	Management & Regionality.	2022
Luis Ángel Correa García.	Gastronomic tourism, factors that affect the competitiveness of restaurants in Zacatecas, Mexico.	Tourism and Heritage.	2022

Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

Results

In Table 2, it will be possible to contemplate the authors of the selected articles, their objectives, materials and methods, as well as their results.

The scientific articles presented address the relationship between tourism and gastronomy, focusing on the contributions of several authors on this topic in recent years. The first point highlighted is the diversity of themes present in scientific articles on tourism, with greater emphasis on studies on the potential of tourist destinations or products capable of promoting tourism. In the background, studies on the interests, motivations, degree of satisfaction and profile of tourists stand out. Other issues of less recurrence include the attraction of investments, the intersection between sectors, the role of affective memory, socially responsible consumption and competitiveness factors.

The relationship between tourism and gastronomy has been a topic that has been increasingly addressed since 1990, when tourism began to recognize gastronomy as an important attraction and motivation for tourists, especially after the year 2000. The articles selected for the study refer to a period of 10 years, from 2012 to 2022, indicating a trend of greater research on gastronomic tourism in recent years.

Gastronomic tourism is analyzed from different perspectives. Long (2018) is cited for his contribution in discussing the connection between cultural tourism, ethical cooking companies, and cultural policies, highlighting gastronomy as a vehicle for the historical identity of a region or country. This view is related to the concept of identity, which, according to Chaui (2000), is essential for something to be recognized and preserved.

Valdez and Fontecha (2018) bring an interesting perspective by emphasizing the role of gastronomy as an instrument for strengthening both tourism and the cultural identity of local populations. Cunha (2018) also addresses gastronomy as a strategic product with high potential for the development of tourism. Torres and Aparicio (2018) complement this view by analyzing gastronomic tourist itineraries, with the aim of obtaining detailed information about typical dishes, thus contributing to the promotion and dissemination of these tourist destinations.

Finally, Verduzco and Valenzuela (2018) deal with the urban transformations associated with the creation of gastronomic-tourist districts, highlighting the challenges faced in urban planning and conflict management. The construction of these districts can generate gentrification processes, impacting the urban dynamics of certain spaces. This aspect of urban transformations becomes central to the debate on the impact of gastronomic tourism on cities.

The set of reviewed studies demonstrates how gastronomic tourism has consolidated itself as an important aspect within the tourism sector, with implications not only for economic development, but also for the preservation and appreciation of local culture.

The authors Medeiros; Cunha and Passador (2018), analyze gastronomic tourism from a typical regional product, demonstrating failures in the dissemination of products, which are offered in order to attract tourists. To the Cross¹; Carrión and Cruz² (2018), the studies focus on diners in two gastronomic areas of Mexico City: the city center and the gastronomic district. Where they conclude, that in both places, the diners were then satisfied, due to the diversity of the menus. The representativeness of the places is also characterized, on the one hand, the center is described as a traditional space, of spontaneous, neglected and chaotic growth. On the other hand, the gastronomic district is more organized, with a modern gastronomic offer, both national and international.

The works address the relevance of gastronomic products in the promotion of Brazilian tourism, highlighting several approaches and research that discuss the impact of gastronomy on tourism. The theme is explored by different authors, who analyze gastronomy not only as a tourist attraction, but also as an important tool for the economic and cultural development of local communities.

Martins, Amorim and Schluter (2012) point out that Brazilian gastronomy occupies a secondary role in tourism promotions, and is often neglected in promotional materials. In contrast, other studies (Torre, Morales-Fernandez, and Naranjo, 2012; Bahls and Farias, 2015) recognize the potential of gastronomy to positively influence the economic and cultural development of communities, highlighting its role in preserving cultural identity through food, which can bring different cultures closer together.

Authors such as Peccini (2013), Goes, Mascarenhas and Medeiros (2019) highlight that gastronomy can be a main, complementary or supportive attraction for tourism, while Cunha (2018) presents it as a strategic product for tourism development.

In addition, affective memory related to gastronomy is discussed by Sartori, Cruz and Tricarico (2021), who associate food with hospitality and the evocation of symbolic values and emotions, creating a nostalgic experience that connects the past and the present. Typical foods and native foods, addressed by Llano (2017) and Torres and Aparicio (2018), are recognized for their cultural importance, representing the identity of a place and its history.

The concept of gastronomic tourism is approached under various nomenclatures, such as “culinary tourism” (Torre, Rojas and Romero, 2016), “food tourism” (Cunha, 2018) and “oleotourism” (Moral-Cuadra et al., 2020). Competitiveness between tourist destinations is also mentioned, with gastronomy playing a key role in making a location stand out from other tourist destinations (Verduzco and Valenzuela, 2018).

These studies highlight the growing importance of gastronomy in the context of tourism, both as a cultural attraction and as a factor of regional development, reflecting the complexity and multifunctionality of this practice in the tourism scenario.

Chang, Okumus, and Chiu (2021) investigate the concept of “culinary vacations” in the context of Taiwanese tourism, highlighting that culinary activities can promote aspects of local cuisine, such as preparation methods and the use of regional medicinal plants. In addition, the authors suggest that these culinary experiences can enrich the experience of tourists by providing an immersion in the cultural elements of the region.

On the other hand, authors such as Peccini (2013) and Sartori, Cruz and Tricarico (2021) address gastronomic tourism as a means of promoting intangible heritage values. For these scholars, gastronomy is seen as an essential part of the cultural experience of a region, and the commitment of local, regional and national authorities to the preservation and promotion of local gastronomy is fundamental. Without this commitment, the authors warn, cultural values can be lost over time.

Torre, Morales-Fernandez, and Naranjo (2012) and other researchers, such as Millan, Torre, and Rojas (2021), investigate the socioeconomic profile of tourists seeking gastronomic experiences. These studies reveal that gastronomic tourism not only contributes to the development of gastronomic routes, but also to economic growth, through the generation of employment and income. In addition, tourists looking to experience gastronomic experiences are often motivated to explore the regional culinary characteristics.

Authors such as Contreras and Medina (2021) see gastronomic tourism as an extension of rural tourism, connecting tourists with local gastronomy and its preparation methods. This type of tourism also contributes to the development of social responsibility and the sharing of cultural values. Millan, Torre, and Rojas (2021) also note that gastronomic tourism can help reduce the seasonality associated with sun and beach tourism, providing an alternative during off-season periods.

Finally, Llano (2017) highlights the importance of valuing traditional food and typical dishes, promoting tourist itineraries that recognize local recipes and ways of preparation. This type of tourism, which connects with the culinary traditions of a region, can strengthen cultural identity and awareness of the importance of preserving original flavors.

Regarding research methods, most articles in Portuguese and Spanish use qualitative approaches, while studies in English combine qualitative and quantitative methods. Most studies analyze gastronomic tourism from an economic perspective, highlighting its potential to add value and build customer loyalty. However, authors such as Kesimoglu (2015) point out that this economic view can reduce the richness of the theme, by focusing only on economic potential and competitive advantages, neglecting essential cultural aspects of gastronomic tourism.

In short, food tourism emerges as a multifaceted tool that can not only boost the local economy but also promote cultural preservation and social responsibility.

Table 2. Information on the articles analyzed.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ARTICLES ANALYZED IN PORTUGUESE			
Author(s) / year	Objective	Materials and methods	Results
Uiara Martins; Ericka Amorim; Regina Schluter (2012).	Realize the relevance that the gastronomic product has for the promotion of Brazilian tourism abroad.	Exploratory research. Using the bibliographic survey as a methodological procedure. For the development of the empirical study, a collection of promotional material was carried out from destinations that included gastronomy as an offer. They are: Amazonia, Bahia, Brasília, Gramado (Rio Grande do Sul), Ipojuca (Pernambuco), Natal (Rio Grande do Norte), Niterói (Rio de Janeiro), Olinda (Pernambuco), Pará, Pernambuco, Rio de Janeiro, Rio Grande do Sul, Santa Catarina, São Luís (Maranhão), São Paulo.	In this analysis, it was concluded that Brazilian gastronomy occupies a secondary role in the promotions of destinations. In addition to having a minimal presence in tourist brochures, which allow tourists to learn about basic aspects, such as the composition and name of local dishes, where to eat or historical-cultural contexts in which they are part of the local cuisine.
Rosana Peccini (2013).	It seeks to discuss and expand the multiple possibilities to think about food in terms of its relations with tourism activity.	The analysis of the article is multidisciplinary, through the interpretation of specialists who think about food as an expression of the identity of a certain social group, building from there, an interface with tourism.	It is concluded that among the contributions of gastronomy to the tourist activity, its reflection as intangible heritage stands out. And regarding its performance in current times, at times it supports tourism, but in other cases it is the main tourist attraction.
Jaqueline Munchen; Roslaine Kovalczuk de Oliveira Garcia (2015).	Investigate travelers' interest in gastronomic elements.	Exploratory research. With the application of a questionnaire, with closed questions, with people who have traveled more than three times, nationally or internationally, in the last two years.	In this analysis, it is concluded that 81% of the respondents seek to know the typical gastronomy of the places visited on their tourist trips. 36% consider typical gastronomy very important, while 58% consider it important.
Álvaro Augusto Bahls; Rodolfo Wendhausen Krause; Fernanda de Souza Farias (2015).	Compare the foreign panorama with the Brazilian national one and identify the main variables considered by destinations and managers when implementing a gastronomic tourism enterprise.	The research is exploratory. And it uses the comparative method. As a data collection technique, a documentary and bibliographic research is carried out, from the databases of the Google Scholar and EBSCO websites.	It is concluded, in this study, that the existing plans for the implementation of a tourist gastronomic enterprise, have generic information, about the general panorama of local gastronomy, with some bureaucratic issues for opening a company and some statistics about customer preference. Thus, there are few articles that detail the procedures for opening a catering establishment.
Charllys Lima; Sueli Moreira; Alicia Cabral; Caroline Silva; Maria Luiza Mesquita (2016).	To analyze the Redinha Market as a potential gastronomic tourist, through the commercialization of gíngua with tapioca, a typical dish of the city of Natal.	This is a quantitative, descriptive study. Using as a data collection technique a form composed of 15 questions, answered by 31 market users. For the analysis, the questions were organized into categories.	In this study, the lack of basic infrastructure was found as a negative point, whereas positive points were fair price and good service. Most of the interviewees would recommend the market to other people, and the male interviewees are attracted by the gíngua with tapioca, in order to meet with friends during the week.
Lucy M. Long (2018).	To offer an overview of the intersection of cultural tourism, ethnic culinary enterprises, and cultural policies.	It is an academic essay, using books, published articles and magazines as a theoretical basis.	It is concluded that gastronomic tourism projects show food as carriers of identity and history. Noting that the selection of interpretations about these foods reflects issues of power. And ethnicity makes this issue even more complex.
Mirna de Lima Medeiros; Júlio Araújo Carneiro da Cunha; João Luiz Passador (2018).	Analyze the gastronomic tourism related to artisanal Minas cheese from Serro.	This is a case study with the use of various instruments: interviews (14), questionnaire (109 valid) and bibliographic and documentary research. Data analysis was performed by means of descriptive statistics and content analysis.	The present study points out that the tourist flow cannot be attributed to the existence of artisanal Minas cheese from Serro. The results indicate that for 72.8% of the people, cheese was not the motivator for the visits. 63.1% already knew the cheese before the visit. The interviewees made several points regarding the development of gastronomic tourism. It was found that local producers were interested in participating in the tourist trade.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ARTICLES ANALYZED IN PORTUGUESE			
Author(s) / year	Objective	Materials and methods	Results
Chayenne Goes; Rúbia Gisele Tramontin Mascarenhas; Mirna de Lima Medeiros (2019).	Check if gastronomy is part of Paraná's tourism promotion.	This is an "exploratory-descriptive" research. Secondary data were used for data collection.	It is concluded that gastronomy is part of the tourism promotion of Paraná, in a superficial way. It was verified that the image projected by the Paraná Tourism Secretariat, uses gastronomic elements as tourist attractions (main or complementary), while the city hall uses gastronomic elements as support equipment.
Maria Henriqueta Sperandio Garcia Gimenes Minasse (2020).	To understand how research on Gastronomic Tourism has been developing, based on the analysis of scientific production published in Brazilian journals dedicated to tourism and hospitality with a Qualis CAPES evaluation equal to or higher than B5.	This is a qualitative research, based on principles of content analysis (Bardin 2011), with an analytical corpus of 89 articles published between 2005 and 2017.	The magazines Rosa dos Ventos and Turismo em Análise published the largest number of articles; 24.71% of the articles belong to the B1/Qualis stratum; The peak of publications was 2017 (16.85%). 8 themes and 11 sub-themes were identified, highlighting Gastronomy as a Tourist Attraction and Beverage Tourism. Beverage Tourism/wine tourism was the most developed theme (28.09%).
Anderson Sartori; Rosana Arruda Cruz; Luciano Tricarico (2021).	To analyze the possibilities of applying the concept of affective food memory to gastronomic tourist destinations.	The research is qualitative and exploratory, with bibliographic research in tourism and other areas of knowledge related to the theme. Categorical content analysis was used.	It is concluded that the affective food memory contributes to the appreciation of the receiving communities and the preservation of material and immaterial heritage.
Elisangela de Farias; Adrielly Souza Silva; Marconi Freitas da Costa (2022).	To measure how the intention to visit eco-gastronomic destinations could be influenced by socially responsible consumption, social influence and eating habits.	This is a quantitative research and the research strategy used was the online survey. The data were treated through Structural Equation Modeling (MEE).	It is concluded that when consumption is socially responsible, the social influence and eating habits of tourists do not seem to motivate interest in visitation. Contrary to what was expected by the theoretical assumptions.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ARTICLES ANALYZED IN ENGLISH			
Author(s) / year	Objective	Materials and methods	Results
Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Ricardo Hernández Rojas; Virginia Navajas Romero (2016).	To evaluate to what extent the offer of gastronomic products from Córdoba (Argentina) can be considered of high quality and differentiated, which can serve as a basis for the development of tourism products.	The research is qualitative, using field research as data collection, based on visits to different catering establishments (64) to learn about what is offered in the city of Córdoba. Analysis of the information collected by the Córdoba Tourism Observatory and the Andalusian Statistical Institute to predict and model the evolution of gastronomic tourism in Córdoba.	In this study, it is concluded that gastronomic tourism in Córdoba has great potential, because it shows a growing trend, in part because of the existing gastronomy, which can be enjoyed in taverns, restaurants and hotels, but also, for generating new jobs and wealth in the city. Gastronomic tourism in the city of Córdoba is a booming segment that complements architectural cultural tourism.
Sandra Cunha (2018).	To promote the strategic product Gastronomy, as a tourist product of excellence with high potential for the development of Portuguese Tourism.	Qualitative research, analyzing various events of related studies and correlating the main ideas and doctrines, focusing on the importance of Gastronomic Tourism, gastronomic events for regions and gastronomic routes as a factor Differentiator.	It was found that there are not many studies related to the contribution of gastronomy in the development of the regions. Portugal should, like Spain and France, structure its gastronomic product as a product that gives authenticity and quality to Portugal. Gastronomy and wines are considered qualifying assets of the Portuguese tourist offer.
Salvador Moral-Cuadra; Raquel Acero de la Cruz; Ramón Rueda López; Enrique Salinas Cuadrado (2020).	To deepen the relationship between the motivation of the tourist and the gastronomic experience acquired in the case of oleotourism in southern Spain, by a model of structural equations.	Quantitative methodology based on primary sources, including a survey based on other works previously published. A questionnaire was used as a form of data collection. For data analysis, structural equation-based models (SEM) were used.	The positive influence of motivations on the tourist's subsequent gastronomic experience was established, in line with previous studies. It was observed that public-private partnerships are essential for the preservation of rural areas as new gastronomic destinations.
Genoveva Dancausa Millán; Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Ricardo Hernández Rojas (2021).	To analyze the profile of food tourists in Andalusia (southern Spain) to understand their motivations and estimate the demand for food tourism using seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (SARIMA) models.	Quantitative research, where a field study was carried out. A questionnaire consisting of 23 questions was applied to tourists from Andalusia. A univariate and bivariate descriptive analysis was performed.	It is concluded that the predominant profile of gastronomic tourists in Andalusia comprises in greater numbers the male sex (54.6%), aged 50 to 59 years (38.6%), high school (64.3%), average income between 1,500 and 2,000 euros (35.1%), working for others (67.7%), married (48.1%), travels gastronomic routes with a partner (43.2%).

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ARTICLES ANALYZED IN ENGLISH			
Author(s) / year	Objective	Materials and methods	Results
Janet Chang; Bendegul Okumus; Chih-Hung Wang; Chien-Yin Chiu (2021).	Investigate how the concept of culinary holidays can be used by tourism authorities and practitioners in Taiwan (China).	Qualitative approach using the Delphi method and the analytical hierarchy process (AHP). A number of indicators of culinary holiday experiences were established from the literature and interviews.	It is concluded that in addition to the well-known Taiwanese cuisine currently served in restaurants, holiday culinary activities can divulge more elusive aspects, such as local cooking methods and medicinal applications of local plants. In addition to making the kitchen a central tourist product and not an external one. Incorporating unique meals and places into culinary holiday curriculums, such as the "midnight snack" ouxiaoye – a smelly tofu hunt at night markets – will leave food fans adventurous, with an unforgettable experience.
Luis Ángel Correa García (2022).	Determine the factors that can help restaurants be more competitive in the face of a health crisis.	The research is quantitative, non-experimental, cross-sectional and correlational-causal. Documentary review was used. The sample is non-probabilistic due to the characteristics of the research. A questionnaire was carried out virtually, consisting of eleven questions, with 158 people as respondents, in a restaurant with a tourist vocation.	It is concluded that intangible resources are important to increase the competitiveness of restaurants, especially in a business that offers food and dishes with authenticity and attachment to the customs of the region, the efficiency of the service is a significant variable. Price is not an important factor for customers because usually the gastronomic tourist has a high economic level.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ARTICLES ANALYZED IN SPANISH			
Author(s) / year	Objective	Materials and methods	Results
Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Emilio J. Morales-Fernández; Leonor María Pérez Naranjo (2012).	To know the socioeconomic profile of the tourist who demands gastronomic tourism and the existing offer of it, in the gastronomic routes existing in the province of Córdoba.	Quantitative research, where fieldwork was carried out based on two types of survey, the supply survey and the demand survey. A questionnaire with 35 questions was applied to tourists from Córdoba. Using as a statistical technique, frequency analysis, correlations and contingency tables.	It was found that the majority socioeconomic profile of gastronomic tourists in the province of Córdoba is: male (55% of the sample), over 45 years of age (54%), with high school education (93%), income Available between 1,001 and 1,500 euros (53%), status married civil (44%) and belonging to the urban area (92%). It was found that 68% of respondents do not stay overnight in the area due to the reduced hotel infrastructure. The results obtained indicate that a professionalization of the sector is necessary, and that it is a type of tourism that can generate additional income for farmers and create jobs, especially in times of crisis.
Genoveva Millán Vázquez de la Torre; Luis Amador; Juan Manuel Arjona Fuentes (2016).	Gather information that serves to promote the aforementioned denomination as a gastronomic route and thus increase the sources of income and employment of the local population.	Qualitative research. Fieldwork was carried out with the application of a questionnaire with 35 questions, with tourists who seek to learn about the production process of Iberian ham or participate in its fair, in Villanueva de Córdoba.	It is concluded that the development of gastronomic tourism, aiming at Iberian ham, will contribute to integrate the traditional primary function with the specialized tertiary. It will contribute to the increase in the average expenditure of visitors and increase in jobs and average income of the local population.
Fabián Andrés Llano (2017).	To provide food inputs that can be patrimonialized, to build bridges between the generation of tourist itineraries and the products of the land, through the recognition of recipes, techniques and dishes characteristic of the cultural gastronomy of Nemocón (Colombia).	It is a qualitative research. A documentary review was carried out, using oral history as a methodological strategy. The work was carried out following the parameters of ethnography. Interviews with inhabitants who work with tourism were also applied.	A range of local products associated with the figure of Chief Nemequene, who, in addition to being remembered by the residents of the municipality, is a character that allows a connection between food, culture and local history. It is concluded that the rescue of food preparation techniques linked to culture can reorient tourist itineraries, consolidating gastronomic tourism in the municipality.
Luz Mary Castellón Valdez; Joaquín Fontecha Fontecha (2018).	To analyze gastronomy as an instrument with which tourism can be enhanced and to highlight the cultural identity of the people of Santander (Spain).	Descriptive and exploratory research. Using bibliographic and documentary analysis. As data collection techniques, direct observation and semi-structured interviews and the application of questionnaires were used.	The results obtained allowed us to propose an initial design of a route in Santander, as a strategy to promote tourism in the region. It is concluded that gastronomic tourism can become an important source of employment and opportunities for the population of the municipalities that will make up the gastronomic route in Santander.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ARTICLES ANALYZED IN SPANISH			
Author(s) / year	Objective	Materials and methods	Results
María Teresa Kido Cruz; Isis Arlene Díaz Carrión; Antonio Kido Cruz (2018).	Conducting a survey among diners in the two most important gastronomic areas in the city of Tijuana, Mexico: the city center and the gastronomic district, in addition to briefly characterizing both places, measures the degree of customer satisfaction, as well as identifying the specific factors that determine it.	Quantitative research. Non-participant observation was performed. A structural equation model (SLM) with five constructs and 13 observed variables was used, as well as an importance matrix (IPMA) was used for the quantitative analysis.	It is concluded that, in general, diners are satisfied. On the one hand, the Center can be described as a traditional space, of spontaneous, neglected and chaotic growth, while the neighborhood is characterized by being a more organized space with a modern gastronomic offer, national and international. Among the main factors that determine this degree of satisfaction are the diversity of the menu and the preparation of the space for the Gastronomic District.
Basilio Verduzco; Basilia alenzuela (2018).	To analyze the phenomenon of the formation of gastronomic-tourist urban districts (excavated) as part of the transformation of large cities.	It is an academic essay, using books, published articles and magazines as a theoretical basis.	The article identifies challenges for public policies and negotiation processes aimed at resolving controversies associated with the search for a better position of cities on the global economic map.
María del Carmen Navarrete Torres; Cecilia García Muñoz Aparicio (2018).	Analyze some aspects of gastronomic tourism, especially the itineraries recognized as gastronomic and obtain information about the typical dishes that are prepared and with the information obtained, propose strategies to achieve greater dissemination.	It is a qualitative research, which used bibliographic and documentary research as a form of data collection.	The results obtained made it possible to learn about the gastronomic offer, as well as the regions that are included and the main dishes that are part of Mexican cuisine considered a World Heritage Site.
Daniel de Jesús Contreras; F. Xavier Medina (2021).	To analyze the possibilities and prospects for the development of gastronomic tourism of the Mexican Designations of Origin (DO) of foodstuffs.	It is an exploratory and descriptive research work. A SWOT analysis matrix was used. The research is characterized as qualitative and a bibliographic and documentary research was carried out.	It is concluded that gastronomic tourism can contribute to the positioning of the DOs, to boost trade and strengthen the production chains, but public policies and mixed funds will be necessary to stimulate the development of the rural environment.

Source: Prepared by the survey, 2022.

Use of materials and methods

The authors of the analyzed articles define the methodological procedures adopted for the elaboration of their studies. From these statements, it was possible to compile a description of the methodologies used in the 25 selected articles, which contributes to a deeper understanding of the methods employed and their application in the specific contexts of each research.

This version presents a clearer and more formal organization, adapted to the style of scientific texts, with a well-defined separation between the points of convergence and divergence, as well as a conclusion about the methods used.

The use of SWOT, Relative Importance Matrix, Case Study, Multidisciplinary, Comparative Method, Delphi Method and Indicators were also mentioned once.

The methodological affiliation of the articles is not clear, and even less so their epistemological foundations. Methods such as Max Weber's individualism, where subjectivities are shaped by their social scenarios (2001). Or even, according to the epistemological typology presented by Adam Schaff, about the paradigms of the process of knowledge, contemplating the objectivist, subjectivist and interactive (dialectical) model. That for Kant (1724-1804), the interactive model is dialectical, but still abstract and idealistic. For Hegel (1770-1831), the process of knowledge is dialectical, but now historical and no longer abstract, according to Kantian schematism. In Marx (1818-1883) and Engels (1820-1895), knowledge is objectified in a dialectical, historical, and materialist way. They are not addressed, making them poor, from a methodological point of view.

Discussion of the results

The text presents a comparative analysis between different articles, highlighting both the points of convergence and the points of divergence found in the authors' approaches to cultural identity, symbolic values and socioeconomic development related to gastronomy and tourism. The following is a restructuring and improvement of the text with a scientific focus, maintaining its essence:

Table 3. Methodological procedures.

Kind	Quantity
Bibliography, bibliographic and documentary survey	12
Statistical procedures (descriptive, univariate and bivariate descriptive, frequency analysis, contingency table, correlation, structured equation modeling)	9
Use of questionnaire or survey	9
Qualitative	8
Quantitative	7
Exploratory	5
Use of interviews and oral history	4
Direct observation	3
Content Analysis (categorical)	3
Essay	2

Source: Prepared by the survey, 2022.

Points of convergence

By comparing the articles analyzed in Portuguese, English and Spanish, it was possible to identify several points of convergence, which reflect a common direction between the different approaches. These points reveal central aspects that permeate the articles, such as the importance of cultural identity, represented through food, methods of preparation, spices and the relationship with the environment. According to Fagliari (2005), this identity can be consolidated in different ways, such as through gastronomic itineraries, fairs, museums, bars, restaurants and regional events.

Cultural identity, in turn, makes room for another identified point of convergence: the symbolic values associated with food. These values are represented by memories, emotions, ways of life and the relationship with the environment. Long (2018) reinforces the importance of food as a fundamental element for the preservation of cultural traditions, highlighting that the consumption of typical regional dishes provides an immersion in the historical and cultural context to which the food is linked.

In addition, both cultural identity and symbolic values contribute to another point of convergence: socioeconomic development. By strengthening the brand of tourist destinations and their territoriality, food is fundamental for economic growth and cultural appreciation, as discussed by Florida (2002). Gastronomy, by attracting tourists in search of authentic experiences, can boost local development, creating a virtuous cycle that benefits a destination's economy and culture.

Points of divergence

The analysis of the articles also allowed the identification of significant divergences between the authors' points of view. One of the divergent aspects refers to the urban transformations resulting from the development of gastronomic-tourist centers. Verduzco and Valenzuela (2018) offer a perspective focused on urbanism, addressing the formation of urban space through ways of life and the relationship with the surroundings. The discussion covers the phenomenon of gentrification, a process in which residents of peripheral areas are displaced due to the valorization of these regions, transforming them into more affluent areas (Smith, 2006). This process entails economic, social and cultural changes in the urban environment.

Another point of divergence is related to public policies to strengthen the local economy through gastronomy. Verduzco and Valenzuela (2018) advocate the implementation of effective public policies that strategically position localities in the global economy. This point of view contrasts with that of other authors, such as Florida (2002), who focuses on strengthening the brand and territoriality of a destination at the national level. The difference lies in the international perspective, which is based on the dissemination of the "brand" (territory) through gastronomy, with the aim of building loyalty and attracting international tourists.

Thus, the dialogue proposed by Verduzco and Valenzuela (2018) expands by contemplating different aspects of urbanization and economic development, bringing a perspective that until then had not been approached in the same way in the other articles analyzed.

Final considerations

The problem that motivated this research was to understand how gastronomic tourism has been contemplated in academic productions at the national and international level. Thus, the objective of this research was fulfilled, since, from the analyzed articles, it was possible to raise a dialogue about the literature of gastronomic tourism, which will possibly contribute with more critical thoughts around the theme.

Studies on gastronomic tourism have been growing in recent years, and its contemplation gains different types of approaches, as demonstrated throughout this research. From the variety of nomenclatures, to studies that analyze the profile of visitors, consumer behavior and urban planning in gastronomic districts. However, in general, they present a weakening in relation to methodological affiliation and epistemological foundations.

All the articles analyzed contemplated gastronomy for the preservation of local culture, even if subjectively and often aiming only at economic issues. Symbolic values and socioeconomic development are concentrated in all the articles analyzed, each with its respective approaches, which refers to the value of gastronomic tourism and its potential.

The selected articles also bring important reflections on the role of gastronomy in tourism. Even today, Brazilian gastronomy occupies a secondary role in the promotions of destinations. In some studies related to the English language, it is the main attraction, complementary or supportive. And in studies in Spanish, gastronomy is presented as a strategic product for tourism development.

There are, however, recent initiatives in Brazil on the importance of gastronomy in tourist destinations. Recently, the I International Seminar on Gastronomic Tourism was held in Paraty and the Ministry of Tourism launched the document – Trends in Gastronomic Tourism in Brazil. Our communication vehicles are full of programs around gastronomy and gastronomic festivals proliferate in the country, as well as formal and informal gastronomy courses.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Bahls, Á. A., R. W. K., & Farias, F. D. S. (2015). Gastronomic planning in tourist destinations: A comparison between the national and foreign panorama. *Compass Rose*, (June), 223–241. Retrieved from <http://www.ucs.br/etc/revistas/index.php/rosa-dosventos>
- Canesqui, A. M., & Garcia, R. W. D. (2005). *Anthropology and nutrition: A possible dialogue*. Rio de Janeiro: Fiocruz.
- Chang, J., Okumus, B., & Chiu, C.-H. W.-Y. (2021). Food tourism: Cooking holiday experiences in East Asia. *Tourism Review*, 76(5), 1067–1083. Retrieved from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/TR-09-2019-0399/full/html>
- Chauí, M. (2000). *Invitation to philosophy*. São Paulo: Ática.
- Contreras, D. D. J., & Medina, F. X. (2021). Gastronomic tourism, typical agri-food products and designations of origin: Possibilities and expectations of development in Mexico. *Journal of Tourism and Heritage Research*, 4(1), 343–363. Retrieved from <https://heritagesciencejournal.springeropen.com/>
- Cruz, M. T. K., Carrión, I. A. D., & Cruz, A. K. (2018). Diner satisfaction as a key element of the gastronomy-tourism binomial in Tijuana. *Social Studies, Mexico*, (June 28), 1–25. Retrieved from <https://www.ciad.mx/estudiosociales/index.php/es/article/view/499>
- Cunha, S. (2018). Gastronomic tourism, a differential factor. *Millenium, Portugal*, (January 18), 93–98. Retrieved from <https://revistas.rcaap.pt/millenium/article/view/13067>
- Fagliari, G. S. (2005). *Tourism and food: Introductory analysis*. São Paulo: Roca.

- Florida, R. (2002). *The rise of the creative class: Its role in transforming work, leisure, community, and everyday life*. New York, NY: L&PM.
- Gil, A. C. (2002). *How to develop research projects*. São Paulo: Atlas.
- Goes, C., Mascarenhas, R. G. T., & Medeiros, M. D. L. (2019). Sabores do Paraná: Análise da promoção turística. *Spheres*, 15, 33–45. Retrieved from <https://portalrevistas.ucb.br/index.php/esf/article/view/10534>
- Kesimoglu, A. (2015). A reconceptualization of gastronomy as relational and reflexive. *Hospitality & Society*, 5(1), 71–92. Retrieved from <https://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/intellect/hosp/2015/00000005/00000001/art00005>
- Kosík, K. (1969). *Dialectic of the concrete*. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra.
- Lakatos, E. M., & Marconi, M. A. (2003). *How to develop research projects*. São Paulo: Atlas.
- Llano, F. A. (2017). Gastronomy, tourism and territorial potentialities: The mining dish and salting, bases for food tourism in Nemocón. *Revista Colombiana de Geografía*, (July 2), 295–306. Retrieved from <https://revistas.unal.edu.co/index.php/rcg>
- Long, L. M. (2018). Cultural policies in gastronomic tourism with ethnic foods. *Revista de Administração de Empresas - RAE*, 58(3), 316–324.
- Martins, D., Jr, C. A. D., & Fonseca, F. T. (2012). Geocoding of urban addresses with quality indication. *GEOINFO, Campos do Jordão*, (November), 36–41. Retrieved from <http://mtc-m16c.sid.inpe.br/col/sid.inpe.br/mtc-m18/2012/12.04.13.23/doc/furtado.pdf>
- Martins, U., Amorim, E., & Schluter, R. (2012). The promotion of Brazilian gastronomy in tourist brochures – An analysis of the case of the Lisbon Tourism Exchange (BTL 2012). *Rosa dos Ventos*, 3(September), 335–351. Retrieved from <https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/4735/473547090005.pdf>
- Medeiros, M. D. L., Cunha, J. A. C. D., & Passador, J. L. (2018). Gastronomic tourism and regional development: A study based on the case of artisanal Minas cheese from Serro. *Virtual Tourism Dock*, 18(2), 173–194. Retrieved from <http://www.ivt.coppe.ufrj.br/caderno/index.php/caderno>
- München, J., & Garcia, R. K. D. O. (2015). The interest of travelers in the gastronomic elements of tourism. *Conhecimento Online*, 1(7), 94–103. Retrieved from <https://periodicos.feevale.br/seer/index.php/revistaconhecimentoonline/article/view/90>
- Peccini, R. (2013). Gastronomy and tourism. *Compass Rose*, (June), 206–217. Retrieved from <https://www.ucs.br/site/revistarosadosventos/>
- Sartori, A., Cruz, R. A., & Tricarico, L. (2021). Affective food memory: A concept for the development of experiences for gastronomic tourism. *Compass Rose*, 1–20. Retrieved from <http://www.ucs.br/etc/revistas/index.php/rosadosventos/article/view/9034>
- Smith, N. (2006). Generalized gentrification: From a local anomaly to urban “regeneration” as a global urban strategy. In C. Bidou-Zachariassen (Ed.), *Back to the city: From gentrification processes to the policies of “revitalization” of urban centers* (pp. 60–87). São Paulo: Annablume.